

Phased Array Parameter Optimization for Low-Altitude Targets

by

G. V. Trunk, J. D. Wilson, and P. K. Hughes II
Radar Division
Naval Research Laboratory
Washington, DC 20375

Abstract - This paper investigates optimal integration times, search strategies, and confirmation strategies for an X-band, pulse-Doppler, phased array radar which is performing the horizon surveillance function.

INTRODUCTION

From the systems point of view, beam agility is the main thing that distinguishes a phased array radar from a mechanically scanning radar. Beam agility can be used to have (a) a longer integration time and hence more sensitivity in a given direction and/or (b) a variable search or track update rate. In this paper, the problem of how best to use the flexibility of a phased array radar to detect low-altitude targets at the horizon will be considered. Previously, Billam [1] considered the optimization of some parameters of a phased array radar performing volume surveillance. However, for horizon surveillance of low-altitude targets (within the horizon null), the returned signal power varies much more rapidly than $(1/R)^4$ and consequently the previous results [1] where the returned power varies as $(1/R)^4$ are not applicable. In the next section, the system concept and the radar system are briefly described. This is followed by three sections which give results for integration time, search beam separation, and confirmation strategy. The last section is a brief summary.

RADAR AND SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

In this paper, we will consider an X-band, phased array radar[2] which performs horizon surveillance, engagement functions, and dedicated target tracking, and responds to cues (e.g. IR or ESM). For most of the paper, unless otherwise indicated, it will be assumed that 50% of the time is available for horizon search. The

power-aperture product is sufficient to detect a 1m^2 target in free space at a range in excess of 50 nmi. In the search mode, the radar uses a medium-prf, pulse-Doppler waveform whose prf varies between 20 and 32 kHz. During search, a single prf is used in all beam positions. The prf is changed from scan to scan to obtain different blind speeds and eclipsed ranges. During search the basic coherent integration time is increased by 1 over the cosine squared of the angle off boresight to compensate for the loss of antenna gain. If a threshold crossing, which does not correlate with any existing track, is obtained, the radar transmits a set of N coherent bursts at different prf's in order to confirm the existence of a target. The prf's of the N coherent bursts (and hence, blind speeds and eclipsed ranges) only differ by a small amount from the prf on which the initial search detection was made in order to minimize the probability that the target will be in the blind speeds and eclipsed ranges of the N coherent bursts. A target is confirmed if an additional two detections are obtained on the confirmation bursts. The unambiguous range and velocity of the target can be obtained by applying the resolution algorithms discussed in references [3] and [4]. Generally, three detections (i.e. the initial search detection and the two confirmation detections) are required to resolve the range and velocity ambiguities. If there is a long time between these detections, the range movement can be accounted for by using a long term integration algorithm [2] that accounts for target movement.

INTEGRATION TIME/SCAN TIME

Throughout this paper, the measurement of performance will be the 90th percentile firm track initiation range. For any given set of conditions, 1000 repetitions are performed; a histogram of the 1000 track

initiation ranges (obtained via simulation of the radar, the signal processing, and the scenario) is generated; and the 90th percentile firm track initiation range is extracted. A typical histogram of the firm track initiation ranges for a low-altitude, supersonic target is shown in Fig. 1. For the 1000 repetitions, the maximum firm track initiation range is 10.3 nmi, the minimum firm track initiation range is 7.0 nmi, and the 90th percentile firm track initiation range is 7.94 nmi.

Figure 1. Histogram of firm track initiation range. 90th percentile firm track initiation range is 7.94 nmi.

For any radar, there is a trade off between integration time and search rate (i.e. scan time). If one doubles the integration time in all search positions, the time to search a given volume will also double. The optimal integration time is a function of the radar's power-aperture product, the number of search beam positions, the apparent radar cross section as a function of range (the apparent radar cross section is very low for low-altitude targets within the horizon null), and the target's speed. With respect to target speed, a mach 2 target travels approximately 1 nmi in 3 seconds and a mach 3 target travels approximately 1 nmi in 2 seconds. Consequently, for supersonic, low-altitude targets which break the radar horizon around 10 nmi, it will be extremely important to scan the horizon rapidly. The results of 90th percentile firm track initiation range versus integration time for a supersonic target are shown in Fig. 2. In this example, it was assumed that the target has a Rayleigh fluctuating cross section and that 50% of the time was available for horizon search - the other 50% of the time is used for dedicated tracking, engagement functions and responding to cues. Furthermore, during confirmation the same target cross section is obtained for all confirmation dwells; however,

this value is different from the target cross section during search. Figure 2 indicates that there is an optimal integration time around 3 ms which corresponds to a scan time around 0.5 seconds. For longer integration times, the scan time is longer; and the supersonic target moves so far during a scan that the track initiation range decreases. Figure 3 shows the results when 100% of the time was available for horizon search. The optimal integration time is around 6 ms which again corresponds to a scan time of 0.5 seconds. Thus, the more fundamental parameter seems to be scan time not integration time. For supersonic targets the optimal scan time is approximately 0.5 seconds.

Figure 2. Ninetieth percentile firm track initiation range and scan time as a function of the integration time. Horizon search commands 50% of the radar's time.

Figure 3. Ninetieth percentile firm track initiation range and scan time as a function of the integration time. Horizon search commands 100% of the radar's time.

BEAM SEPARATION

In this section, the optimal separation of search beams will be considered. If the beams are separated by a beamwidth, adjacent beams cross over at their 3-dB points. The trade off is that the closer the beams, the smaller the loss in antenna gain, versus the larger scan time resulting from putting search beams closer to one another requiring more search beam positions to cover a given volume of space. The results of varying the beam separation are shown in Fig. 4. As can be seen the 90th percentile firm track initiation range is essentially independent of beam separation. This is because on every other scan of the horizon, the beam positions are shifted 1/2 of a beamwidth. Thus, if on one scan a target is at the beam cross over point (i.e. minimum antenna gain), on the next scan the target is at the center of a beam (i.e. maximum antenna gain). If the beams are not shifted 1/2 beamwidth on every other scan, Fig. 5 gives the track initiation results. In this figure it can be seen that the optimal beamwidth cross over point is less than a beamwidth (in the range of 0.6 to 0.8 beamwidths).

Figure 4 Ninetieth percentile firm track initiation range and scan time as a function of the search beam cross over point. Successive scans off set by 1/2 beamwidth. Horizon search commands 50% of the radar's time.

CONFIRMATION

In this section the confirmation strategy will be examined. In the basic confirmation strategy, five confirmation dwells are transmitted and two further threshold crossings are required to declare a target. Furthermore, in the baseline configuration the integration time for each dwell is doubled (increased from 3 to 6 ms) to increase the probability of detection. Thus, 10 times more energy is used in confirmation than search. This is possible since the false alarm probability in any range-Doppler cell is only 10^{-7} and this results in approximately only 1 false alarm per scan. So much

Figure 5 Ninetieth percentile firm track initiation range and scan time as a function of the search beam cross over point. Successive scans identical (i.e. no off set). Horizon search commands 50% of the radar's time.

more energy is used in confirmation than search in order to put targets in track as soon as possible. To see how well this is accomplished, consider Fig. 6 which shows the number of confirmation attempts (initiated by target threshold crossings) required to initiate the track. This figure indicates that 730 times the target was initiated from the initial threshold crossing, 211 times a second set of confirmation beams were required, 44 times a third set was required, 10 times a fourth was required, and finally a fifth set of confirmation beams was required once. It is interesting to note that 4 times the correct target was confirmed from a set of confirmation beams initiated by a false alarm in the direction of the

Figure 6 Histogram of number of confirmation attempts required to initiate a track. Ninetieth percentile firm track initiation range is 7.94 nmi.

target. Figure 7 shows the number of confirmation attempts for the 100 smallest track initiation ranges. It is seen that almost 60% of these case required more than one confirmation attempt.

Figure 7 Histogram of number of confirmation attempts required to initiate the smallest 100 firm track ranges.

In an attempt to improve this situation several things were tried. First, six instead of five confirmation dwells were used and these results are shown in Fig. 8. Comparing Figs. 6 and 8 one notes that essentially nothing is gained by adding an extra confirmation dwell.

Figure 8 Histogram of number of confirmation attempts required to initiate a track when six confirmation dwells are used. Ninetieth percentile firm track initiation range is 7.97 nmi.

Next, it was assumed that we had enough frequency diversity to obtain an independent sample of the radar cross section on each of the five confirmation dwells. This result is shown in Fig. 9. It is noted that (a) 870 times the target was initiated on the first confirmation and (b) the 90th percentile firm track initiation range was raised from 7.97 nmi to 8.14 nmi. To further

Figure 9 Histogram of number of confirmation attempts required to initiate a track when frequency diversity decorrelates target cross section dwell to dwell. Ninetieth percentile firm track initiation range is 8.14 nmi.

illustrate that the success of confirmation is mainly a function of the target fluctuation model, a non fluctuating target model was considered and the results are shown in Fig. 10. For this case, 985 times the target was confirmed on the initial attempt and the firm track initiation range was increased to 8.45 nmi.

SUMMARY

In this paper, we have considered the optimization of some parameters of a phased array radar performing horizon search as one of its functions. It was shown that (a) the optimized scan time was approximately 0.5 seconds for a supersonic target and the coherent integration time should be adjusted to obtain the 0.5 seconds scan time, (b) the system performance is essentially independent of the search beam overlap when successive scans are off set by 1/2 beamwidth, and (c) confirmation is mainly a function of the target fluctuation model.

Figure 10 Histogram of number of confirmation attempts required to initiate a track for a non fluctuating target. Ninetieth percentile firm track initiation range is 8.45 nmi.

REFERENCES

1. E. R. Billam, "Parameter Optimisation in Phased Array Radar", RADAR 92, Brighton, 12-13 October 1992
2. G.V. Trunk, J. D. Wilson, and P. K. Hughes II, "Long Term Integration using a Phased Array Radar", IEEE 1990 International Radar Conference, pp 313-315, Washington DC, May 1990
3. G. V. Trunk and S. M. Brockett, "Range and Velocity Ambiguity Resolution", 1993 National Radar Conference, pp 146-149, Boston, MA, April 20-22, 1993
4. G. V. Trunk and M. W. Kim, "Multiple Target Ambiguity Resolution", 1994 National Radar Conference, pp 91-94, Atlanta, GA, March 29-31, 1994